

Supplementary materials

Supplementary figures

Figure S1 - Example of the categorization as Viral, Shared, Cellular or Unknown for six enVhogs (named A to F). For each enVhog, displayed as columns, its presence in cellular species (sp1 to sp5) are first determined using similarity searches and are further used to define a measure of Cellular presence, or Cp. Numbers and formula are detailed for the enVhog on the right (enVhog F) whose

Cp is 0.05. Then, the presence of each enVhog in viral clades (cl1 to cl5) are determined (MMseqs2) and are used to compute a measure of Viral presence, Vp. The Vp of enVhog F is 0.18. Cp and Vp are then used to compute the Viral Quotient (VQ).

Figure S2 - schematic explanation of the iterative procedure used to define the category of each enVhog based on the category of the contigs in which they are encoded. Seven contigs are represented, each encoding four proteins that were clustered into 13 enVhogs displayed in colors at the top left. Each enVhog is categorized independently using Cp and Vq values (step 1a) and then, contigs are classified based on the most abundant category of the enVhog they encode (step 1b). The category of enVhogs was then refined using the category of the contigs on which they appear, and so on (steps Xa and Xb).

Figure S3 - Venn diagram of the viral contig prediction of our manually assembled contigs by VirSorter2, Vibrant and DeepVirFinder. Contigs kept in EnVhogDB lie at the intersection of at least 2 out of 3.

Figure S4 - Taxonomic affiliation of the 53 million deduplicated proteins.

Figure S5 - Clustering structure. The 53.6 million protein sequences were grouped into enVhogs using a three step clustering procedure. The cumulative number of proteins per cluster size are displayed for clusters at each step, named shallow, standard and deep clusters, these last clusters corresponding to enVhogs and singletons. Half of the proteins are grouped respectively in clusters containing more than 2, 42 and 131 sequences.

Figure S6 - Sequence diversity in EnVhogDB clusters: NEFF values were calculated for all enVhogs and compared to the one of protein families from the reference databases PHROG and UniClust30. On the x-axis, the categories correspond to the number of sequences in the cluster (as computed by HHblits after redundancy reduction).

Figure S7 - distribution of enVhogs in the four categories (Viral, Shared, Cellular and Unknown). Number of enVhogs in the four categories (Y-axis, in log-scale) according to their Viral quotient (Vq) in the x-axis. Bars on the left correspond to enVhogs with no hit in viral and cellular databases and no hit against the viral protein database. EnVhogs are classified as Viral if their Vq is greater than 0.8 or if they were identified as viral hallmarks.

protein class at it. 0 -> Contig post class -> protein class at it. 1

Figure S8 - Evolution of cluster classes in our iterative algorithm taking advantage of genomic context. Left column: Original cluster class, center column: Posterior contig class (V/B/U), rightmost column: Posterior cluster class after 1 iteration. With a single iteration, most of the proteins belonging to enVhogs of category U got an assigned category in V/C/S. To generate the final classification 3 iterations of this algorithm have been run.

Supplementary information

SI1: Similarity search, clustering and HMM generation parameters

Redundancy reduction step (i.e. deduplication):

Linclust parameters: `-c 0.99 --cov-mode 1 --seq-id-mode 1 --cluster-mode 2 --min-seq-id 0.99 -e 0.001 --kmer-per-seq 100`

Shallow clustering:

Linclust parameters: `-c 0.95 --cov-mode 1 --seq-id-mode 1 --cluster-mode 2 --min-seq-id 0.9 -e 0.001 --kmer-per-seq 100`

Standard clustering:

MMseqs2 cluster module, parameters: `-s 4 --min-seq-id 0.3 --cov-mode 0 -c 0.7 -e 0.001 --cluster-mode 0 --cluster-reassign`

Deep clustering (profiles from standard clustering step):

MMseqs2 search module (profile-sequence search): `--add-self-matches -a -s 4 -e 0.001 --cov-mode 0 -c 0.60`

MMseqs2 clust module, parameters: `--cluster-mode 0`

Multiple sequence alignments were generated using MUSCLE, or if the cluster was too big or the alignment too large, MMseqs2 alignment against central sequence of the cluster was used.

HHmake with option -M50 was used to generate the HMMs.

SI2: Pseudo-count computation

The viral proportion V_p can suffer from little representation of viral proteins in databases. For instance if a protein P is identified in a single viral clade C , and C contains only one viral genome in the reference database, then a naive computation of V_p as the ratio of number of genomes in the clade containing the protein P over the total number of genomes in the clade would lead to a V_p of 1.

Adding prior information in the context of small data is crucial to have a reliable measure of the viral proportion. A standard way to cope with this issue is simply to add pseudo counts to the number of genomes in the clade. These pseudo counts vanish relatively to the real count as soon as the reference database contains enough viral genomes in the clade.

We decided to calibrate the pseudo counts so that one ends up with a reliable assessment of the “viralness” in the extreme case of a single representative genome in the clade. In particular, we want the viral quotient to be less than 0.8 as soon as the hostness ($=C_p$) is greater or equal to 1%, which would make the category of the protein either Cellular, Shared or Unknown according to the classification scheme described in the subsection “Material & Methods - Estimating the viralness of each enVhog” of the main paper.

Let α be the pseudocount parameter. For a protein of interest P, when there is a single homolog in the viral reference database, with a single viral genome in its clade, one has:

$$V_p = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha}$$

In this case, as soon as the cellular proportion of the protein is non-trivial (say $C_p > 1\%$), we want the VQ to be low enough not to classify the protein as viral. According to our scheme, VQ has to be lower than 0.8. This induces a lower bound constraint on the pseudocount. Indeed, if the hostness is $> 1\%$, the viral quotient is:

$$VQ \leq \frac{\frac{1}{1+\alpha}}{\frac{1}{1+\alpha} + 0.01}$$

If we want to upper bound the viral quotient by 0.8, then we have the following equation:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{1+\alpha}}{\frac{1}{1+\alpha} + 0.01} < 0.8$$

Which is equivalent to:

$$\alpha \geq \frac{\frac{1}{0.8} - 1}{0.01} - 1 = 24$$

We therefore set the pseudocount parameter to 24.

When homologs of the protein of interest are present in different clades, the pseudocount parameter is equally spread among the clades, hence ending up with the formula:

$$V_p(enVhog) = \frac{1}{\#similar\ clades} \sum_{C:similar\ clades} \frac{\#viruses\ with\ \geq 1\ similar\ protein\ in\ C}{\#viruses\ in\ C + \frac{24}{\#similar\ clades}}$$

SI3: Iterative class assignment

1 Assignment of categories to contigs

As most of the proteins have been classified as Unknown in the previous section, we leveraged co-localization information of clusters on contigs to tag contigs as either Viral, Cellular (contamination), Hybrid or Unknown.

We assigned each contig to a class according to the following (stringent) criteria:

- 1 If the contig contains a majority of protein of category V (i.e. $\#V > \#C + \#S + \#U$ on this contig) -> tag the contig as Viral
- 2 If the contig contains a majority of protein of category C (i.e. $\#C > \#V + \#S + \#U$ on this contig) -> tag the contig as Cellular
- 3 If the contig contains a majority of protein of category U (i.e. $\#U > \#V + \#S + \#C$ on this contig) -> tag the contig as Unknown
- 4 Else it is tagged as H (hybrid contig, containing a mixture V, C and U proteins)

Note that for contigs there is no shared (S) class as they are either from a viral or bacterial genome.

Then we can leverage the contig classes to annotate the proteins on the newly labeled contigs.

2 Bayesian modeling of the contig counts

For a given enVhog, let N be the number of annotated contigs (of category V/C/H) carrying this enVhog. We model the number of contigs n_v, n_c, n_h ($N = n_v + n_c + n_h$) broke down by category as a multinomial distribution parameterized by p_v, p_c, p_h :

$$n_v, n_c, n_h \mid N, p_v, p_c, p_h \sim \text{Mult}(N, p_v, p_c, p_h)$$

More precisely, p_v, p_c, p_h depend only on the category (V/S/C/U) of the enVhog. So if k is the category of the considered enVhog, one gets:

$$n_v, n_c, n_h, n_u \mid N, k \sim \text{Mult}(N, p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h)$$

Rigorously, by setting an uninformative Dirichlet prior distribution on $p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h$ (for each k in $\{V, S, C, U\}$), one gets a Dirichlet posterior distribution on $p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h$ when seeing the data for all enVhogs of each category. Since there is a large number of enVhogs, the posterior distribution is sharply peaked around its mode, and the posterior distribution of the $p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h$ is constant to:

$$p^{(k)}_v = \# \text{ contigs V carrying an enVhog of category k} / \# \text{ contigs}$$

And similarly for other contig categories C and H.

Thus, after having inferred this way the $p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h$ for each category k in $\{V, S, C, U\}$, we are able to compute the likelihood for a given enVhog to be in the category k :

$$p(n_v, n_c, n_h \mid N, p^{(k)}_v, p^{(k)}_c, p^{(k)}_h)$$

In particular, we can compute the ratio:

$$R = p(k=V \mid n_v, n_c, n_h, N, p^{(V)}_v, p^{(V)}_c, p^{(V)}_h) / p(k=C \mid n_v, n_c, n_h, N, p^{(C)}_v, p^{(C)}_c, p^{(C)}_h)$$

Using Bayes' rule:

$$R = p(n_v, n_c, n_h \mid k=V, p^{(V)}_v, p^{(V)}_c, p^{(V)}_h) \cdot p(k=V) / p(n_v, n_c, n_h \mid k=C, p^{(C)}_v, p^{(C)}_c, p^{(C)}_h) \cdot p(k=C)$$

By replacing with the multinomial distribution formula, we simply get:

$$R = p(k=V)/p(k=C) \cdot [p^{(V)}_V / p^{(C)}_V]^{n_V} \cdot [p^{(V)}_C / p^{(C)}_C]^{n_C} \cdot [p^{(V)}_H / p^{(C)}_H]^{n_H}$$

Where the prior $p(k=V)$ is straightforwardly inferred from the total counts:

$$p(k=V) = \# \text{ enVhogs of category V} / \# \text{ enVhogs}$$

And similarly for $p(k=C)$.

3 Iterative algorithm for assigning enVhog categories

For each uncertain enVhog (i.e. of category S or U), we computed the R ratio of V and C categories and apply the following decision:

- 1 If $R > 5$, the enVhog is labeled as V
- 2 If $R < 1/5$, the enVhog is labeled as C
- 3 Else the category remained unchanged (S or U) since we do not have enough evidence to decide on the category

Finally, for enVhogs labeled as C, we force them back to category S if their hostness is below 5% (indeed indicating that the protein is not well conserved in cellular genomes).

After the new category has been set to each envhog, we recomputed the contig categories using the scheme described in the previous section a.

We ran 3 iterations of this scheme, recomputing a fresh ratio R based on the contig and enVhog categories of the previous iteration.